

FLORISTIC COMPOSITION AND WEED SEED BANK IN INTENSIVE AND EXTENSIVE CULTIVATION OF VINE GRAPE

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*SUMMARY: Floristic composition of weed species occurs as the companion of cultivated plants, including vine grape as a perennial culture. Knowledge of weed seed banks in agro-eco systems of certain region enables better choice of cultivation practices, as well as rational herbicide use. In the period 2011-2012 studies of floristic composition and weed seed banks in vine grape grown both intensively and extensively were performed. The aim of the study was to determine the relation of floristic composition and weed seed bank in vine grape plantations with different cultivation practices. In addition to the farming operations of soil tillage, intensive cultivation method would involve also herbicide use and extensive farming would involve all cropping operations without herbicide use. Soil samples for determination of weed seed bank were taken at the beginning and at the end of the growing season from each plot in ten replications. Samples were taken from different depths of the arable soil layer, i.e. from 0-10 cm, 10-20 and 20-30 cm (Conn, 1987; Sharratt, 1998). Despite great diversity of weed species, whose seeds were determined from the samples, only few weed species dominated with a greater number of seed, and these were *Amaranthus retroflexus* L., *Portulaca oleracea* L., *Chenopodium album* L., *Stellaria media* (L.) Vill. and *Lamium purpureum* L.*

Key words: weed seed bank, vine grape, method of growing, extensive, intensive.

INTRODUCTION

Weed seed bank in the soil represents the past and potential future of the size of weed seed community above the soil surface (Swanton and Booth, 2004). According to Baker (1989), definition of "seed bank" is that "it is seed quantity in the soil capable to

Original scientific paper / *Originalni naučni rad*

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germinate, to give new life to annual and perennial plants". The type of soil and cultivation have great influence on the quantity of weed seed in the soil. Understanding of weed seed bank is necessary for improvement of studies of weed population dynamics or for establishment of weed control programs (Ambrosio et al., 2004). According to its floristic composition and structure, vineyard weed community belongs amid communities of weed field row crops and orchards (Konstantinović, 2011). The grapevine (*Vitis vinifera* L.), whose numerous varieties are used for production of grapes belongs to the family *Vitaceae*. Weeds that occur in vineyards have extremely adverse effect both on the vineyards that are in establishment, as well as on the older vineyards. Cultivation practices include autumn and spring inter-row soil cultivation, as well as cultivation during a vegetation period. Studies of weed seed bank size and composition can provide information on past and present weed populations, which contributes to development of forecast system of future potential problems in agricultural production. The study showed that weed communities, in addition to the methods applied for weed control on agricultural production areas are also under great influence of external factors (Buhler et al., 2000; Cardina et al., 2002). Weed seed density, as well as the quantity, to a great extent depend upon soil type, previous crops, soil cultivation, and certainly upon herbicide use (Konstantinović et al., 2008). The aim of this study was to determine differences in weed seed bank of extensive and intensive cultivation of vine grapes, as well as differences in floristic composition of these two ways of growing. Despite different ways of cultivation in the vine rows and in between vine rows in both systems of vine grape growing, the method of sampling was the same, as well as the method of analysis.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

During 2012 at site Erdut, the analysis of weed floristic composition was performed in several vineyard localities, of both extensive and intensive vine grape cultivation. With the aim of establishing weed seed bank, in addition to the analysis of floristic composition, spring soil sampling was performed within the lines and between vine grape lines. Soil sampling on one plot was performed in ten replications, and always from depths of 0-10, 10-20 and 20-30 cm. Each sample contained approximately 3 kg of the soil that was sieved through a series of copper sieves of 0.25 mm in diameter. This was followed by separation of weed seeds from samples, and their determination (Skender et al., 1998). Determination was done by microscopes and weed identification guides. Data processing was performed according to the method of Conn (1987) and Sharratt (1998).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the studied site in intensive and extensive vineyards 33 weed species were found: *Amaranthus retroflexus* L., *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L., *Chenopodium album* L., *Convolvulus arvensis* L., *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers., *Datura stramonium* L., *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) Beauv., *Euphorbia cyparissias* L., *Euphorbia helioscopia* L., *Galium verum* L., *Geranium dissectum* L., *Hibiscus trionum* L., *Iva xanthifolia* Nutt., *Lamium purpureum* L., *Papaver rhoeas* L., *Poa annua* L., *Polygonum aviculare* L., *Polygonum persicaria* L., *Portulaca oleracea* L., *Setaria glauca* (L.) Beauv., *Setaria*

viridis (L.) P. B., *Solanum nigrum* L., *Sorghum halepense* (L.) Pers., *Stachys annua* L., *Stellaria media* (L.) Vill., *Veronica arvensis*, *Taraxacum officinale* Web., *Viola tricolor* L., *Sinapis arvensis* L., *Rumex crispus* (L.)-Medic., *Capsella bursa-pastoris* L., and *Anthemis arvensis* L. In terms of life forms, 22 weed species were represented by therophytes (T), 4 by geophytes (G), 3 by hemicryptophytes (H) and 4 by therophytes/hemicryptophytes (Th) (Table 1).

Table 1. Floristic composition of weed species in extensive and intensive grapevine plantations

WEED SPECIES	Extensively	Intensively	Life form
<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i> L.	+	+	T
<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i> L.	+	+	T
<i>Chenopodium album</i> L.	+	+	T
<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i> L.	+	-	G
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	+	+	G
<i>Datura stramonium</i> L.	+	+	T
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) Beauv.	+	+	T
<i>Euphorbia cyparissias</i> L.	+	+	H
<i>Euphorbia helioscopia</i> L.	+	+	T
<i>Galium verum</i> L.	-	+	G
<i>Geranium dissectum</i> L.	+	+	T
<i>Hibiscus trionum</i> L.	+	-	T
<i>Iva xanthifolia</i> Nutt.	+	+	T
<i>Lamium purpureum</i> L.	+	+	Th
<i>Papaver rhoeas</i> L.	+	+	T
<i>Poa annua</i> L.	+	+	T
<i>Polygonum aviculare</i> L.	+	-	T
<i>Polygonum persicaria</i> L.	+	+	T
<i>Portulaca oleracea</i> L.	+	+	T
<i>Setaria glauca</i> (L.) Beauv.	+	+	T
<i>Setaria viridis</i> (L.) P. B.	+	+	T
<i>Solanum nigrum</i> L.	+	+	T
<i>Sorghum halepense</i> (L.) Pers.	+	+	G
<i>Stachys annua</i> L.	+	+	T
<i>Stellaria media</i> (L.) Vill.	+	+	Th
<i>Veronica arvensis</i>	+	+	T
<i>Veronica hederifolia</i> L.	+	+	T
<i>Taraxacum officinale</i> Web.	+	+	H
<i>Viola tricolor</i> L.	-	+	Th
<i>Sinapis arvensis</i> L.	+	+	T
<i>Rumex crispus</i> (L.) – Medic.	+	+	H
<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i> L.	+	+	Th
<i>Anthemis arvensis</i> L.	+	+	T

(+) Determined, (-) Undetermined. (+) Pronađeno, (-) Nije pronađeno.

Soil cultivation can have great influence on seed distribution in the soil profile (Anderson *et al.* 1998; Sosnoskie *et al.* 2006). On the chosen sites of Erdut in 6 vineyards, seeds of the following weeds in weed seed bank were not found: *Taraxacum officinale* Web., *Viola tricolor* L., *Sinapis arvensis* L., *Rumex crispus* (L.)-Medic., *Capsella bursa-pastoris* L., and *Anthemis arvensis* L. The following fourteen weed species were determined: *Portulaca oleracea* L., *Amaranthus retroflexus* L., *Stellaria media*

(L.) Vill., *Chenopodium album* L., *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) R. et Sch., *Hibiscus triominum* L., *Polygonum aviculare* L., *Datura stramonium* L., *Setaria glauca* (L.) Beauv., *Setaria viridis* (L.) Beauv., *Stachys annua* L., *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L., *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers., and *Lamium purpureum* L. In the top soil layer of 0-10 cm there was a significantly higher number of seeds per m², including three weed species: *Portulaca oleracea* L. (5627), *Amaranthus retroflexus* L. (5263) and *Chenopodium album* L. (4125). In the last five years in intensively cultivated vineyards weed control has been performed in the vine rows, by herbicides glufosinate-ammonium and glyphosate. Annually, treatments were performed once with the allowed concentrations of glyphosate for perennial crops, as well as three times by herbicide glufosinate-ammonium. In the top soil layer the number of seeds per m² was 16669, while in the other two layers the number of weed seeds was almost equal, but significantly lower in comparison to the top layer. In the layer of 10-20 cm the number of weed seed was 11.538 per m², and in the layer of 20-30 cm it was 11.454 weed seeds per m².

Between vine rows 10 weed species were found: *Portulaca oleracea* L., *Amaranthus retroflexus* L., *Stellaria media* (L.) Vill., *Chenopodium album* L., *Iva xanthifolia* Nutt., *Poa annua* L., *Veronica hederifolia* L., *Setaria viridis* (L.) Beauv., *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers., and *Lamium purpureum* L. In the top soil layer, it was five weed species that had a higher number of seeds in relation to other species and layers of the sampled soil, i.e. *Portulaca oleracea* L. (3931), *Amaranthus retroflexus* L. (3712), *Stellaria media* (L.) Vill. (2871), *Chenopodium album* L. (2987), and *Lamium purpureum* L. (1755). In the top soil layer the seed quantity was significantly higher, numbering 15974 seeds per m², in comparison to the other two layers of 10-20cm and 20-30 cm of depth. In the soil layer of 10-20 cm 9139 seeds per m² were found, while in the layer of 20-30 cm 11831 seeds per m² were found.

In systems with reduced tillage, weeds have a tendency to produce a significantly higher number of seeds in top layers than in systems with intensive cultivation (du Croix Sissons *et al.* 2000; Dyer 1995; Soriano *et al.* 1968). In systems with no-tillage, seeds remain on the soil surface, exposed to inconvenient conditions that reduce or increase germination capability, depending on the species (Chauhan *et al.* 2006). In the row of extensively grown vineyard 16 weed species were found: *Portulaca oleracea* L., *Amaranthus retroflexus* L., *Stellaria media* (L.) Vill., *Chenopodium album* L., *Euphorbia helioscopia* L., *Galium verum* L., *Polygonum persicaria* L., *Datura stramonium* L., *Setaria glauca* (L.) Beauv., *Solanum nigrum* L., *Stachys annua* L., *Geranium dissectum* L., *Veronica arvensis* L., *Euphorbia cyparissias* L., *Convolvulus arvensis* L., and *Sinapis arvensis* L. In the top soil layer of 0-10 cm a significantly higher number of seeds had three weed species, *Portulaca oleracea* L., numbering 7736 seeds per m², *Amaranthus retroflexus* L., numbering 3669 seeds per m², and *Chenopodium album* L. with 5264 seeds per m², in relation to 10 other species that were also found in this soil layer. In comparison to other two layers, the top soil layer contained significantly higher quantity of weed seed numbering in total 19380 weed seeds per m². In the vine row of extensive vineyard the number of weed seeds decreased with increased soil depth.

In between line area of extensive vineyard, 14 weed species were found: *Portulaca oleracea* L., *Amaranthus retroflexus* L., *Stellaria media* (L.) Vill., *Chenopodium album* L., *Polygonum persicaria* L., *Polygonum aviculare* L., *Papaver rhoeas* L., *Geranium dissectum* Just., *Solanum nigrum* L., *Stachys annua* L., *Euphorbia cyparissias* L., *Convolvulus arvensis* L., *Datura stramonium* L., and *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L.

According to the number of seeds in the top layer of 0-10 cm two weed species, *Portulaca oleracea* L. and *Amaranthus retroflexus* L. proved dominant, numbering 6620 and 7577 weed seeds per m², respectively. The top soil layer contained significantly higher quantity of weed seeds, i.e. 15712 per m² in comparison to the other two layers. In the soil layer of 10-20 cm 12601 seeds per m² were determined, while in the layer of 20-30 cm 13.638 seeds per m² were determined.

In the vine row of extensive vineyard there was a greater number of weed species among which the following three were dominant: *Portulaca oleracea* L., *Amaranthus retroflexus* L., and *Chenopodium album* L. A higher number of weed species occurring between vine rows in intensive vineyard suggests that soil cultivation itself equalized and reduced numbers of seeds in the seed bank, while in the vine row there were three weed species with a significantly higher number of seeds in the seed bank in relation to the seed bank in between vine rows of intensive vineyard. In between rows area, simultaneously with herbicide application with glyphosate and glufosinate-ammonium, vine covering and uncovering were performed on a regular basis.

In the vine row of extensive vineyard, according to the number of determined seeds, the following three weed species proved to be dominant: *Portulaca oleracea* L., *Amaranthus retroflexus* L. and *Chenopodium album* L. Two weed species, *Portulaca oleracea* L., and *Amaranthus retroflexus* L., which were dominant in comparison to other weed species, occurred in between vine rows, but in abundance they were almost equal to the number of weed seeds in the vine row. Soil tillage in extensive vineyard was reduced to periodical cultivation or mulching, in the vine rows, as well as between them. Cardina *et al.* (1991) stated that weed seed density in cultivated soils was always composed of several dominant weed species in a high number and several weed species in a moderate or lower number. Results of Uremis *et al.* (2003) suggest that weed seed bank consists of several dominant weed species, but *Amaranthus* sp. was always among them. Results of this study confirmed dominance of weed species *Amaranthus retroflexus* L., but *Portulaca oleracea* L. proved to be dominant as well.

In the rows of the extensive and intensive vineyards, a higher number of weed seeds was found in comparison to the area between vine rows in both vineyard growing systems. In the extensive vineyard, a higher number of weed seed was distributed per m² (Graph 1).

In the vine row of the intensive vineyard, up to depth of 0-30 cm per m², there were 39683 seeds of weed species.

In between vine rows area of the intensive vineyard, up to depth of 0-30 cm per m² there were 36944 seeds of weed species.

In the vine row of the extensive vineyard, up to depth of 0-30 cm per m² there were 43785 seeds of weed species.

In between vine rows are of the extensive vineyard, up to depth of 0-30 cm per m² there were 41951 seeds of weed species.

Graph 1. Total number of weed seeds per m² in the vine row and in between vine row area of the extensive and intensive vineyard.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study suggest that weed seed bank potential was high, with 27 sampled and identified weed species. The number of weed species in the intensive vineyard in the vine row and in between line row area was lower in comparison to the extensive vineyard. It was concluded that intensive mechanical cultivation in between vine row area reduced the number of weed species. The number of weed seeds was also significantly lower in intensive system of vine grape cultivation than in the vineyard of extensive vine growing.

REFERENCES

- ANDERSON, R. L., TANAKA, D. L., BLACK, A. L. and SCHWEIZER, E. E.: Weed community and species response to crop rotation tillage, and nitrogen fertility. *Weed Technol.*, 12:531–536, 1998.
- AMBROSIO, L.A., IGLESIAS, L., MARIN, C., MONTE, J.P.: Evaluation of sampling methods and assessment of the sample size to estimate the weed seed bank in soil, taking into account spatial variability. *Weed Research*, 44:224-236, 2004.
- BAKER, H.G.: The evolution of weeds. *Ann. Rev. Ecol. Syst.*, 5:1-24, 1974.
- BUHLER, D.D., LIEBMAN, M., OBRYCKI, J.J.: Theoretical and practical challenges to an IP approach to weed management. *Weed Science*, 48:274–280, 2000.
- CARDINA, J., HERMS, C.P., DOOHAN, D.J.: Crop rotation and tillage system effects on weed seedbanks. *Weed Science*, 50:448–460, 2002.
- CARDINA, J., REGNIER, E., HARRISON, K.: Long-term tillage effect on seed bank in three Ohio soils, *Weed Science*, 39:186-194, 1991.
- CHAUHAN, B. S., GILL, G. S. and PRESTON, C.: Tillage system effects on weed ecology, herbicide activity and persistence: a review. *Aust. J. Exp. Agric.*, 46:1557–1570, 2006.

- CONN, J.: Effects of tillage and straw management on Alaskan weed vegetation: a study on newly cleared land. *Soil Tillage Res.*, 9:275-285, 1987.
- DU CROIX SISSONS, VAN ACKER M. J. R. C., DERKSEN D. A., and THOMAS, A. G.: Depth of seedling recruitment of five weed species measured in situ in conventional- and zero-tillage fields. *Weed Sci.*, 48:327-332, 2000.
- DYER, W. E.: Exploiting weed seed dormancy and germination requirements through agronomic practices. *Weed Sci.*, 43:498-503, 1995.
- KONSTANTINOVIĆ, B.: Osnovi herbologije i herbicidi. Univerzitet u Novom Sadu. Poljoprivredni fakultet Novi Sad. 2011.
- KONSTANTINOVIĆ, B., MESELDŽIJA, M., KONSTANTINOVIĆ, Bo: Distribution of weed species seed under different crops and in various soil layers. *Polish Journal of Natural science, Supplement No.5. University of Warmia and Mazury in Olszyn, Poland*, pp. 298-299, 2008.
- KONSTANTINOVIĆ, B., MESELDŽIJA, M., KONSTANTINOVIĆ, Bo., MANDIĆ, N.: Ispitivanje banke semena korova pod usevom soje. *Acta herbologica*, 17:171-174, 2008.
- SKENDER, A., i SURADNICI: Sjemenje i plodovi poljoprivrednih kultura i korova na području Hrvatske, Poljoprivredni fakultet, Osijek, 1998.
- SHARRATT, B.S.: Barley yield and evapotranspiration governed by tillage practices in interior Alaska. *Soil Tillage Res.*, 46:225-229, 1998.
- SOSNOSKIE, L. M., HERMS, C. P. and CARDINA. J.: Weed seedbank community composition in a 35-yr-old tillage and rotation experiment. *Weed Sci.*, 54:263-273, 2006.
- SWANTON C.J. i BOOTH B.D.: Management of weed seedbanks in the context of populations and communities. *Weed Technology*, 18:1496-1502, 2004.
- UREMIS, A.M., CHRISTENSEN, S. i SIMMELSGAARD S.E.: Spatial correlation between weed species densities and soil properties. *Weed Research*, 42:26-38, 2002.

**FLORISTIČKI SASTAV I BANKA SEMENA KOROVA
U INTENZIVNOM I EKSTENZIVNOM
GAJENJU VINOVE LOZE**

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Izvod

U agroekosistemima poznavanje banke korovskih semena na određenom području omogućava bolji izbor agrotehničkih mera, kao i racionalniju primenu herbicida. Tokom 2011-2012 godine vršena su ispitivanja florističkog sastava i banke semena korova u zasadu vinove loze, koja je uzgajana po principu intenzivnog i ekstenzivnog uzgoja. Intenzivan uzgoj bi podrazumevao pored svih agrotehničkih operacija obrade zemljišta i upotrebu herbicida. Ekstenzivni uzgoj bi podrazumevao sve agrotehničke operacije bez upotrebe herbicida. Uzorci zemlje za određivanje banke semena korova uzimani su na početku i pred kraj vegetacije, i to sa svake parcele u deset ponavljanja,

iz oraničnog sloja zemlje, posebno sa dubine od 0-10 cm, 10-20 cm i 20-30 cm. Uzeti uzorci zemljišta su ispirani vodom kroz bakarna sita određenih promera i sušeni na sobnoj temperaturi, a zatim je usledilo izdvajanje semena korova i njihova determinacija. I pored velike raznovrsnosti korovskih vrsta, čija su semena determinisana iz ispitivanih uzoraka, samo nekoliko vrsta dominiralo je sa većom brojnošću semena: *Amaranthus retroflexus* L., *Portulaca oleracea* L., *Chenopodium album* L., *Stellaria media* (L.) Vill. i *Lamium purpureum* L.

Ključne reči: banka semena korova, vinova loza, ekstenzivno, intenzivno.

Received / *Primljen*: 12.03.2013.

Accepted / *Prihvaćen*: 04.04.2013.